

Women's Participation in Local Governance among the Zeme Naga tribe in Nagaland: Problems and Prospects

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Abstract: The Zeme Naga women continue to face significant barriers in their participation in local governance. It is largely due to the cultural norms backed by patriarchal customary laws. They prioritise men for leadership roles, and these societal expectations often restrict women to family responsibilities rather than encouraging their involvement in governance. This article will explore the role of traditional institutions alongside modern Local governance and highlight women's participation in local governance. It will also highlight the challenges that the Zeme Naga women faced in participation in local governance. The article concludes by highlighting the amicable strategies for women's empowerment within the structure of local governance.

Key words: Zeme women, Zeme tribe, local governance, traditional institutions, customary laws

1. Introduction

Nagaland is one of the three states where the 73rd Amendment Act, 1992, the three-tier system called the Panchayat Raj is not applicable. As Article 371(A) of the Constitution of India provides special provisions to all Nagas to safeguard their customary laws. The Zeme tribe are one of the Indigenous tribes of Nagaland. They govern their villages by a set of unwritten customary laws of cultural norms and traditions, which are practised and passed down orally through generations. The Zeme Naga's customary laws and traditions often intersect with patriarchal norms. The local self-governance is structured and practised through customary laws and traditions, which usually leads to Zeme Naga women being excluded from important decision-making bodies such as village council administration. The members who participate in the local governance and administration are mostly dominated by male members of the village, leading to instances of bias against women.

Despite women having made significant contributions to the family, community and society, they are often excluded from participating in decision-making, such as in the village council. Women's participation in

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the decision-making process and governance is essential to incorporate their interests as they have different issues, perspectives and outlooks on socio-political issues. Women's exclusion in the decision-making process in private and public affairs governance often maximises the overall marginalisation of women and gender-based equality. This article examines the sociocultural practices and norms that directly and indirectly block women's participation and representation in local political institutions. It highlights potential ways to empower women, particularly in the decision-making process and local governance.

2. Nagaland's Local Governance System.

Nagaland is a tribal state where a combination of informal and formal legal systems guides the local governance and administrative structure and functions. At the village level, there is a tribal council where elders handle the community welfare and conflicts using their customary laws and traditional practices. Such traditional institutions are recognised and accepted by a formal legal system under the Nagaland Village and Area Council Act of 1978. The act provides legal provisions for preserving and practising local governance and administration. Like in any other Indian state, governance at the state level runs through a legislative assembly, executive and administrative branches directly by the state government. The district governance is taken care of by the Deputy Commissioner, and tribal councils are allowed to manage community land, resources, welfare, disputes, etc.

At the grassroots level of administration, there are many challenges since there are no uniform and codified customary laws. It often comes into conflict with formal laws, especially when gender issues, land and natural resources management or distribution, and development are involved. Women remain away from modern and traditional institutions of governance in Nagaland. Gender inequality and women's empowerment are still major issues accompanied by male domination in the administrative system and gender bias in customary laws and traditional norms. Women-oriented infrastructure and resources are limited, and the right of inheritance is with male family members, whereas female has the least or no share at all. At such times, traditional laws have a negative impact on the government's women's empowerment policies.

Despite many limitations of tribal councils and their traditional customary laws that have been passed through generations, tribes are inclined toward these institutions and laws, especially in rural areas. It remains strong and accustomed to the tribes since modern law is complex and expensive to the tribes in dealing with particular in conflict resolution and crime-related matters. A dual legal and administrative system, with both formal and informal laws, can sometimes be a boon for governing the people. The management and implementation of policies and adjudication of conflict are made easier by the dual

system, where formalities find it difficult to deal with informal systems that can easily be settled. Strengthening both systems enhances local good governance practically. In democratic governance, local people's participation is crucial for the government to implement its responsibilities successfully. Tribal leaders and their population have significant roles to play, and the inclusion of the tribal institutions and laws makes the tribe accommodate the state governing system since they are accustomed to it. Thus, the mixed system of institutions and laws still prevails in local governance despite the limitations between the two systems.

3. The Zeme's Socio-Political Culture

Zeme is one of the major tribes in Nagaland, Northeast India. The Zeme settlements are primarily located in the Peren district of Nagaland, the Dima Hasao district of Assam (formerly known as the North Cachar Hills district), Tamenglong, and the Senapati district of Manipur. Many of them also live in other parts of the country and abroad. However, the majority of the Zeme reside in the Peren district of Nagaland (District Peren, Government of Nagaland, n.d.).

The local Governing system among the Zeme tribes is based on the traditional institution governed by their customary laws. Decisions are usually made based on common interests and the welfare of the people. Community interest practices are deeply connected to traditional values, where males often dominate in public responsibilities and decision-making. Male members in the community take up the leadership part in the political sphere in alignment with the hierarchical and patriarchal structure. In such a structure, women do not have much role and autonomy to put forward their rights in the private and public spheres (Samson, 2017).

4. Historical Background of the Traditional Institutions

The Zeme tribe has a decentralised and collective political system rooted in traditional clan-based organisation. The system of clan-based tribal councils leads their governance structure. These tribal councils are male-dominated institutions where leadership positions and their members are largely male.

In every one of the Zeme villages, there are Khels/clans, and each of the Khels/clans has its own Morung. The Morung is a traditional Naga tribal Institution common in northeast India, particularly in Nagaland. The Morung is a traditional bachelor dormitory where male unmarried adults gather and sleep after their day's work. It also served as a place where elders shared stories, taught manners, socialised, and discussed culture, customary laws, and other aspects of their lives. The key role of the Morung as a bachelor

dormitory is to educate unmarried male adults about their customs, traditions, history, warfare, various skills of wood carving, blacksmithing, bamboo crafting, traditional songs, folk tales, dances, etc. There is also Releiki/ Leuseuki called the girl's dormitory, where all the young women sleep, learn the art of weaving, spinning, twisting of the thread, folk song, dances, love affairs and many more. It is an informal education institution where customs, traditions, religious practices, self-discipline, and social values are imparted to the youth (Zeliang, 2015, pp. 26–27). Those were passed down through generations, playing a key role in shaping society and culture.

5. Village Council (VC) and its authorities in the present modern society

With the advancement of Christianity and the introduction of formal modern governance in the tribal areas in Nagaland, Morungs, once used for informal education to impart knowledge to the younger generation, are no longer in practice. The Government of Nagaland enacted the Nagaland Village and Area Council Act 1978 to recognise the local self-governance of the village. Every recognised village in Nagaland is required to have a village council (VC), Goanbura, chairman, secretary, treasurer and other members chosen by the villagers as approved by the state government (Joshi et al., 2016, p. 56).

6. The transition of traditional institutions to a Modern Governance system

The government of Nagaland sought to establish an institutional framework for local governance, as outlined in the Nagaland Village and Area Council Act (1978). Despite this, the Act extended the scope of customary law and traditional councils beyond a peripheral feature. Accordingly, despite the changes, Zeme women in modern governance continue to face obstacles in their political representation.

Although the state of Nagaland has brought into a system of elections of Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) with impressive statutory requirements for women's representation (33 % in recent years), women's empowerment remains elusive, especially in rural regions like the Zeme communities. Lack of political repression is not only a problem in Zeme areas regarding women's involvement in political structures, but cultural blockades are still apparent, as women seeking office engagements or leadership positions at the grassroots level face cultural resistance (Nienu, 2024).

7. Zeme Women's participation in local Governance.

Women's participation in local governance in the Zeme Naga community has been minimal. However, with the introduction of reforms and structural change in local governance, there have been positive changes in women's participation (Newmei, 2018, pp. 290–291; Zeliang, 2015, pp. 25–26).

In today's context of Zeme Naga society in Nagaland, elements like traditional institutions or local customs are still playing roles to frame and undeniably restrict women from availing opportunities, they deem fit. Women are still not allowed to participate in village councils or in the decision-making process. Nevertheless, she plays a persuasive role indirectly through her spouse and male relatives (Lalengkimi, 2024). On June 26, 2024, the ULB (Urban Local Bodies) elections were held after a 20-year-long advocacy and legal battle for a 33% reservation for women. Eleven female candidates from the Zeme Naga tribe from Peren district contested the ULB elections, out of which six female candidates were elected. Among those candidates, the oldest female candidate who has contested and won for the Nagaland ULB elections was Smt Sibeule, 71 years old, of the Zeme Naga tribe from Peren Town. This election result also indicates a mild positive change in the community, and more importantly, for wider society to accept our future generations breaking out of their traditional roles as women leaders within their own village settings or government bodies (Nienu, 2024).

8. Challenges faced by Zeme women

When it comes to political participation, women in the Zeme communities face numerous challenges as noted below. Some of these challenges include:

- a) **Cultural Resistance:** Outdated customary norms and practices that do not allow women to engage in public and politically active areas pull back their participation in governance.
- b) **Lack of Education:** Despite recording some progress in the recent past with regards to female literates, women's literacy levels still fall as compared to men's. A good number of households give preference to the education of their male children, creating a gap in the number of women who are able or willing to get into politics.
- c) **Economic Dependence:** The Majority of Zeme families have been relying on males for the provision of economic resources, and therefore, the women are unable to partake in governance.
- d) **Gender Bias in Political Structures:** Although quotas have been implemented in some local councils to reserve places for women, the local political structure's subservience to male principles detracts from the power and authority embedded in those spots.

9. The prospect of Women's Empowerment in Local Governance

A strong local governance system is crucial in a democratic country like India. To strengthen this system, women's participation is essential. Women play a vital role in raising families and are sources of discipline and public participation. A strong, disciplined society originates from families that are morally and intellectually grounded. Therefore, empowering women in every society is vital.

To further empower Zeme women and promote their participation in local governance, several pathways need to be explored and implemented:

- a) **Educational Empowerment:** Investing in the education of girls and women in Zeme Naga communities will equip them with the skills necessary for effective political participation. Awareness programs that emphasise the importance of women's political rights and leadership can also foster social change. This could include establishing gender-sensitive schools and educational programs that promote equality and respect. To provide scholarships and financial aid to girls and women to overcome economic barriers that prevent many women from accessing education.
- b) **Legal and Policy Reforms:** Expanding reservations for women in all levels of governance, including village councils, can enhance women's visibility and participation in local politics. In the context of Zeme Naga society, this could involve amending the Nagaland Village and Area Council Act. The Act could be amended to mandate a specific quota for women in village councils, ensuring that women have a voice in decision-making processes. There is a requirement for enacting laws against gender-based violence and discrimination to create a safe and supportive environment for women to participate in public life and establish mechanisms for women's representation in traditional institutions.
- c) **Community Awareness:** Campaigns aimed at changing societal attitudes towards women in leadership roles can help reduce cultural resistance. Specific initiatives could include organising community dialogues and workshops. These events can raise awareness about the importance of women's participation in governance and challenge traditional stereotypes. Encouraging male leaders to speak out in support of women's empowerment can help shift societal attitudes. The use of traditional media, storytelling, and cultural performances can be used to convey messages of gender equality and women's leadership.
- d) **Economic Independence:** Promoting women's economic independence through entrepreneurship, microfinance, and vocational training will increase their autonomy and reduce the dependency that often limits political participation. In the Zeme Naga context, this could involve establishing women's cooperatives and self-help groups. These groups can provide women with access to financial resources, training, and support. Government policies and programs can be implemented to encourage and support women's entrepreneurship. Additionally, provide vocational training that enables women to acquire the skills necessary to earn a livelihood and participate in the local economy.

By implementing these pathways, Zeme Naga women can overcome the challenges they face and actively participate in local governance. This will not only strengthen democratic institutions but also contribute to the overall development and well-being of Zeme Naga communities.

10. Conclusion

The Zeme Nagas have a unique system of governance and the traditional institutions of governance existing in the state have been recognised and protected under the constitution, the local governance system is a complex issue of traditional practices, cultural resilience and modern challenges, despite the provision's aim to increase women's participation cultural norms and systematic barriers continue to hinder their involvement there is still very minimal participation of women in local governance causing gender disparity.

The village council plays looking after the welfare of the people in the village, however, the village councils need to be more inclusive in their representation of women, as women likely have more knowledge about the community from the grassroots level, by adopting a more inclusive governance model, the Zeme Naga people can work towards a more equitable and sustainable future, where the voices of all community members are valued and heard regardless of the Gender.

The Zeme Naga tribe's governance system, rooted in traditional institutions, has largely excluded women from political power. However, there are signs of change, driven by legal reforms, educational advancements, and increasing support for women's participation in politics. While cultural barriers remain, emerging opportunities for women's empowerment in local governance hold promise for a more inclusive future. The ongoing efforts to increase women's representation in local governance should be supported by a multifaceted approach that addresses educational, economic, and cultural barriers to women's full participation in the political life of Zeme communities.

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